

ROSEHIP IN BAKING AND ITS EFFECT ON THE BODY

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To improve the taste properties of bread, seeds of certain plants are used (cumin, poppy, anise, coriander, sea buckthorn fruits, etc.), which contain various biologically active substances and give bread a certain taste and aroma. Rosehip *Rosa majbli* is of particular interest as a raw material for improving taste qualities and a source of various biologically active substances. The generic name of rosehip comes from the Greek word "rhodon" - pink. Russian name - because of the sharp and numerous spikes. Popular names: wild rose, svoborina, svorobornik, chiporas, rosehip. Rosehip was well known as a medicinal plant in ancient Greece. In the fourth century BC, Theophrastus in his "Natural History" gave such a detailed description of it that for many centuries it passed from book to book almost unchanged. Ludwig Graeber's herbalist has a recipe from 1563 for using rosehip as a tooth powder to strengthen the gums.

In Uzbekistan, the rosehip fruit (or, as it used to be called, the dogfisher) has also long been used to treat and prevent bleeding gums and as a means for healing wounds. In the XVI-XVII centuries, special expeditions to the Orenburg steppes were even equipped for harvesting rosehip fruits. During the Russo-Turkish war in the first military hospital in Moscow, the wounded were given "svoroborin molasses" to maintain their strength and treat them. Remembering this tradition, doctors of military hospitals during the Great Patriotic War treated wounds with water decoctions of rose hips. Rosehip grows in sparse forests, on the edges, clearings and clearings, among thickets of shrubs and along ravines. It is more common in meadows and valley forests. It is usually part of shrubby thickets in floodplains of rivers, where it forms commercial massifs. Rosehip May - a shrub of the rosaceae family with a height of 200 cm with thin branches covered with shiny brown-red bark. Old branches are brownish-brown. The flower-bearing branches are set with sparse crescent-shaped spikes bent downwards, flattened at the base, usually sitting in pairs at the base of leaf petioles; rarely, the flower-bearing branches are devoid of spikes. Barren branches (especially in the lower part) and turions (one-year-old

sterile shoots) with thin, straight or slightly curved spikes . The leaves are compound, non-pinnate, with 5-7 pairs of lateral leaflets. Leaves are thin, close together, 1.4-6 cm long, 8-28 mm wide, oblong-elliptic or oblong-ovate. The flowers are large, 3-7 cm in diameter, with five rose petals and a five-part calyx; there are many stamens and pistils. Flowers are solitary, rarely 2-3, on short pedicels, 5-17 mm long, with lanceolate bracts. The petals are pale red to dark red. Fruits are spherical or flattened-globose, rarely ovate or elliptical, smooth, orange or red, fleshy, topped with remaining sepals. Blooms (depending on the area of growth) in May-July; fruits ripen in August-September. Rosehip is propagated by seeds and vegetatively - offspring and green cuttings. Vegetative propagation provides the cheapest and fastest harvesting of rosehip fruits, and also allows the selection of its highly productive forms.

Rosehip fruits are harvested from August (sometimes from the end of July) to October. They collect mature fruits that are not damaged by diseases. It is recommended to collect fruits before full maturity, when they are still hard, but already have a bright red or orange color. Perfectly ripe fruits are picked by hand, carefully, as they are easy to crush, and then they quickly deteriorate during drying. When collecting fruit, it is recommended to wear gloves or tarpaulin mittens to protect against thorns, and to fold the collected raw materials-tight aprons with large pockets in the front. With an average yield, an adult picker can collect 8-20 kg of fruit in a 7-hour working day, and with a high yield (more than 1 t / ha) on thickets of large-fruited forms of dog rose - up to 34 kg. The picker's labor productivity can be significantly increased if various devices are used: a scoop for collecting rosehip fruits, a fruit collecting mug, a bag, etc. Collect fruits before the onset of frost, since fruits touched by frost lose a significant part of vitamins during thawing. Frozen fruits are collected only when it is possible to put them into processing without defrosting, which ensures good preservation of vitamins. Dry the rosehip fruit as soon as possible after harvesting. They are dried in ovens at a temperature of 80-90 °C or in vegetable dryers, ventilated and often turned over. After drying, the fruits are cleaned of sepals and impurities. In addition to whole fruits called unpeeled, peeled fruits are also harvested. In this case, fresh fruits are cut lengthwise or crosswise before drying and the fruits - nuts and hairs-are removed from them. Well-dried rosehip fruits should retain their natural color, smell and taste, contain no more than 14% moisture, do not get your hands dirty and do not stick together in lumps when squeezed, and do not have an admixture of darkened and moldy fruits .

The yield of dry raw materials depends on the time of harvesting, the type of dog rose and other factors. On average, from 100 kg of raw fruit, 32-42 kg of dry raw materials are obtained.

Rosehip is introduced to culture in the Moscow region, Bashkiria, Altai Territory and other areas. High-vitamin and high-yielding varieties were bred: Vitamin VNIVI, Large-fruited VNIVI, Vorontsovsky 1, etc. [15].

Rosehip is a recognized multivitamin plant. In terms of ascorbic acid content, it ranks first among fruit and berry plants.

100 g of fresh rose hip fruit contains ascorbic acid from 600 to 2881 mg, vitamin P (bioflavonoids) - 200-1500 mg, carotene - 2-5 mg, B1-0.25 mg, B2 (riboflavin) - 0.07-0.6 mg, B9-0.88 mg, K1 (phylloquinone)- up to 1 mg, E (tocopherol)- from 6 to 10 mg. In addition, the pulp of hypanthia contains sugars (8.1-11.6 %), pectins (1.8 - 2.8%), tannins and coloring agents [19]. Seed oil is rich in tocopherols and organic acids. A large set of biologically active substances and their high concentration led to the widespread use of rose hip hypanthia for preventive and therapeutic purposes .

The ascorbic acid content is 2.46-5.20% for the absolutely dry mass, or 3.22-10.84% for their absolutely dry pulp. On average, the fruit pulp contains 9.74 mg % carotene, 14.1% pectin substances, 1.58% citric acid, 23.93% total sugars, 18.56% invert sugars, 5.09% sucrose, 8.92% pentosans .

Seed oil contains 170-200 mg% tocopherols (vitamin E), 10 mg% carotene, as well as linoleic, linolenic, oleic and other acids. Fresh fruits contain about 4% of P vitamins (per dry weight), including flavonoids-quercetin, kaempferol, isoquercitrin, etc. The bark, roots and leaves also contain tannins, but most of them (up to 80%) are found in the galls that appear on the fruit. The maximum content of vitamins C and E, as well as carotene, is observed in mature orange-red, but hard rosehip fruits.

Extracts, syrups, pills, tablets, dragees and other medical preparations are made from the fruits of rosehip May. Preparations from rosehip fruits are used mainly as a multivitamin for hypo- and avitaminosis, especially for avitaminosis C, as well as for various diseases accompanied by an increase in the body's need for vitamins [24].

Rosehip fruits are also part of Traskov's anti-asthmatic medicine, vitamin and multivitamin fees; most often they are used as an infusion for home treatment. In addition, rosehip oil and carotene (containing carotenoids, vitamin E and linoleic acid) are obtained from the fruit. Less commonly, rosehip fruits are used to produce holosas, galascorbin, and ascorbic acid .

Contraindications to the use of high doses of ascorbic acid and other rosehip preparations are thrombophlebitis, endocarditis and circulatory failure.

Rosehip is used for vitaminization of food and products in children's institutions, hospitals and public catering enterprises .

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